

MODELS OF THE PHYSICAL ACTIVITY ACCORDING SELF-EVALUATION OF MEDICAL STUDENTS**Stanislaw Nowak***Doctor**Casimir Pulaski Radom University in Radom, Poland***Ihor Zanevskyy***Professor**Lviv State University of Physical Culture named after Ivan Boberskyj, Lviv, Ukraine***Abstract**

Background and Study Aim. The physical fitness is especially important component of medical students as well, as their skills to evaluate corresponding level. This research aims to develop models of the physical activity according self-evaluation of medical students.

Material and Methods. The International Physical Activity Questionnaires was applied to study self-evaluation of medical students of the first grade (55 males and 184 females). All the students gave their informed consent prior to their inclusion in the study. Details that might disclose the identity of the subjects under study were omitted. Factor analysis was used with a purpose to determined factors of variables for studied battery of tests. Factor Loadings (Unrotated) Extraction: Principal components (Marked loadings are $r > 0.7$). Include condition: 5. calculations and graphical presentation of the studied materials was organized using computer packet Statistica and Excel DATA analysis.

Results. Models of the physical activity according self-evaluation of medical students have been developed using 5 factors for males and 4 factors for female students. Eigenvalues presented male results appear approximately two times greater than corresponding eigenvalues from the female group. All the values (4.555, 2.505, 2.484, 2.045) exceed two. Because results of one variable brought the same values (5 days a week) they were ignored, therefore female group as well as male group were tested with the questionnaire of 14 questions. All the fourteen studied variables showed a high level of variation ($V > 22\%$).

Conclusions. Modeling of the physical activity according self-evaluation of medical students showed their professional preparation. Participation in this research should be considerate as an effective way of education.

Keywords: fitness, questionnaire, modeling, male, female

Introduction

Recently, evaluation of a body height and weight harmony among university students has been studied by S. Nowak and I. Zanevskyy [1]. They evaluated appearance by female medicine students, too [2]. This research aims to develop models of the physical activity according self-evaluation of the medical students. Garcia-Alvarez D. and Faubel R. developed a systematic review strategies and measurement tools in physical activity promotion interventions in the university setting [3]. Objective and subjective investigation of physical activity levels and its relation with socio-demographic characteristics among medical students have been published by Farshbaf-Khalili A. et al. [4]. Abdoli M. et al. determinants of physical activity among female students based on the trans-theoretical model [5].

Lucini et al. (2024) showed a significance of stress, exercise and nutrition assessing the lifestyle in a large cohort of undergraduate students [6]. Kukic et al. described physical activity as a means to improve subjective vitality of university students [7]. Moss S. et al. (2024) studied the associations of physical activity and health-risk behaviours toward depressive symptoms among college students regarding gender and obesity disparities [8]. Johannes C. et al. presented systematic review on the strategies and best practices that enhance the physical activity levels of undergraduate university students [9]. Donnelly S, et al. provided a systematic review on the effectiveness of physical activity interventions in improving higher education students' mental health [10]. Edelmann D. et al. studied physical activity and sedentary behaviour in university students-

the role of gender, age, and field of study, targeted degree, and study semester [11]. Diehl K. et al. discussed comparative physical activity as a global question to assess physical activity among university students [12]. Dąbrowska-Galas M, et al. determined physical activity level, insomnia and related impact in medical students in Poland [13].

Coenen P. et al. determined associations of occupational and leisure-time physical activity with all-cause mortality regarding individual participant data meta-analysis [14]. Brown CEB et al. determined key influences on university students' physical activity as a systematic review using the Theoretical Domains Framework and the COM-B model of human behaviour [15]. Barbosa BCR, et al. studied sedentary behaviour associated with the mental health of university students during the Covid-19 pandemic, and not practicing physical activity accentuates its adverse effects: cross-sectional study [16]. Amornsriwatanakul A. et al. determined multilevel factors associated with physical activity participation among Thai university students [17]. Alahmadi MA et al. studied prevalence of sedentary behaviour among university students in Saudi Arabia [18].

Hypothesis. Males and Females medicine university students are able to use their professional skills in modeling of self-evaluation of the physical fitness.

The purpose of the research was to develop models of the physical activity according self-evaluation of the medical students. This goal was achieved by solving the problems as follow: to provide a self-evaluation

questionnaire of medical students (1); to study the results of physical activity questionnaire (2); to adopt a factor analysis in the study of the problem (3).

Materials and Methods

Participants

Two hundred thirty nine students (184 females 21,9 y.o., and 55 males 22,0 y.o.) of a first education year were interrogated about their physical activity during studying at the university as well, as out of studying. All the students gave their informed consent prior to their inclusion in the study. Details that might disclose the identity of the subjects under study were omitted.

Questionnaire

The International Physical Activity Questionnaires (IPAQ) Form in Polish / English

Var1. Intensywny wysiłek fizyczny (minut tygodniowo) / Intense physical effort (minutes per week)

Var2. Ile było takich dni w przeciętnym tygodniu? / How many such days were there in an average week?

Var3 Ile minut przeciętnie trwał taki wysiłek w ciągu jednego dnia? / How many minutes did such effort last on average in one day?

Var4. Umiarkowany wysiłek fizyczny (minut tygodniowo) / Moderate physical effort (minutes per week)

Var5. Ile było takich dni w przeciętnym tygodniu? / How many such days were there in an average week?

Var6. Ile minut przeciętnie trwał taki wysiłek w ciągu jednego dnia? / How many minutes did such effort last on average in one day?

Var7. Chodzenie lub spacerowanie (minut tygodniowo). / Walking (minutes per week).

Var8. Ile minut przeciętnie trwał taki wysiłek w ciągu jednego dnia? / How many minutes did such effort last on average in one day?

Var9. Ile minut przeciętnie trwał taki wysiłek w ciągu jednego dnia? / How many minutes did such effort last on average in one day?

Var10. AF tygodniowa ogółem (min). / Total weekly AP (min)*

Var11. AF ogółem (h) / Total AP (h)

Var12. Siedzenie i leżanie uwzględniając tylko dni powszednie (minut in 5 dni) / Sitting and lying down taking into account only weekdays (minutes in 5 days)

Var13. Ile takich dni było w przeciętnym tygodniu? / How many such days were there in an average week?

Var14. Ile minut dziennie przeciętnie spędzałeś siedząc lub leżąc? / How many minutes per day did you spend sitting or lying down on average?

Var15. Bezruch ogółem (h). / Total immobility (h)
*AF: Aktywność fizyczna / AP – Physical activity.

Statistical elaboration

Factor analysis was used with a purpose to determined factors of variables for studied battery of tests. Factor Loadings (Unrotated) (Spreadsheet1) Extraction: Principal components (Marked loadings are $r > 0.7$, $p = 0.05$). Include condition: 5. Calculations and graphical presentation of the studied materials was organized using computer packet Statistica and MS Excel DATA analysis.

Results

Statistical parameters of the female group have been presented in Table 1.

Table 1
Results of testing of the physical activity according the IPAQ questionnaire (Females, $n_F=184$)

Statistics	Var1	Var2	Var3	Var4	Var5	Var6	Var7	Var8	Var9	Var 10	Var 11	Var12	Var13	Var14
Max*	360	7	120	600	7	120	720	7	120	930	16	3750	5*	750
Me	30	1	20	80	2	30	210	6	40	390	7	2100	5	420
Min	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	30	1	600	5	120
M	55	2	24	106	2	38	237	5	45	398	7	2246	5	450
SD	67	1	25	106	2	30	135	2	24	195	3	511	0	102
V%	122	95	102	100	68	80	57	31	53	49	49	23	0	23

*Notes: n_F – number of female subjects, *Max* – maximal, *Min* – minimal, *Me* – median, *M* – Arithmetic mean, *SD* – standard deviation, $V=100*SD/M$ – coefficient of variation (%).

Because results of the test Var13 (see yellowed cells in the Table 1) brought the same values (5 days a week) they were ignored, therefore female group as well as male group were tested with the questionnaire

of 14 questions. All the fourteen studied variables showed a high level of variation ($V > 22\%$).

Results of Factor Analysis are organized in Table 2.

Table 2.

Factor analysis results (Females, $n_F=184$)*

Variables	Factors				
	1	2	3	4	5
Var1	0.634	-0.169	0.403	0.581	-0.123
Var2	0.571	-0.193	0.447	0.395	-0.189
Var3	0.578	-0.029	0.244	0.643	0.105
Var4	0.661	0.180	0.377	-0.558	0.158
Var5	0.520	0.098	0.268	-0.522	-0.084
Var6	0.634	0.153	0.346	-0.336	0.376
Var7	0.542	-0.311	-0.766	0.011	-0.062
Var8	0.340	-0.220	-0.201	-0.261	-0.791
Var9	0.423	-0.217	-0.709	0.168	0.432
Var10	0.955	-0.177	-0.188	-0.095	0.000
Var11	0.955	-0.177	-0.188	-0.095	0.000
Var12	-0.221	-0.948	0.170	-0.121	0.079
Var13	-0.227	-0.947	0.173	-0.122	0.083
Var14	-0.227	-0.947	0.173	-0.122	0.083
Expl.Var	4.74	3.08	2.05	1.76	1.07
Prp.Totl%	33.8	22.0	14.6	12.6	7.7

*Note: n_M – females' number

Factor analysis has been provided when Eigenvalues were over one (Fig. 1).

According the 1st factor two tests (Var10 and Var11) showed strong correlation ($r=0.955$); according the second one - Var12 ($r=-0.948$), and the 3rd factor (Var7 and Var9). The 5th factor was presented by the

test Var8 ($r=-0.791$). Factor Loadings (Unrotated) Extraction: Principal components. Marked loadings are $r>0.700$, i.e. strong correlation between variables and factors. Corresponding coefficients in the table are typed with bold numbers, for example **0.955** or **0.709**.

Fig. 1. Percentage income regarding studied factors 1 (33.8%), 2 (22.0%), 3 (14.6%), 4 (12.6%), 5 (7.7%), and the rest as factor 6 (9.3%).

Results of testing of the physical activity according the IPAQ questionnaire are collected in Table 3.

Table 3

Results of testing of the physical activity according the IPAQ questionnaire (Males, $n_M=55^*$)

\Var Stat	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14
Max*	300	5	180	600	6	150	630	7	90	840	14	3600	720	12
Me	30	1	20	120	3	45	180	6	30	450	8	2100	420	7
Min	0	0	0	0	0	0	20	1	15	160	3	1200	180	3
M	71	2	33	156	3	57	227	6	41	454	8	2177	431	7
SD	79	1	36	127	1	40	136	1	22	169	3	593	124	2
V%	112	77	107	81	54	71	60	25	54	37	37	27	29	29

*Notes: n_M – number of male subjects, Max – maximal, Min – minimal, Me – median, M – Arithmetic mean, SD – standard deviation, $V=100*SD/M$ – coefficient of variation (%).

There were only 4 factors (one smaller than in the female study group factors) in the male study group as blue columns on the histogram (Fig. 2). Eigenvalues presented male results appear approximately two times greater than corresponding eigenvalues from the female

group. All the values (4.555, 2.505, 2.484, 2.045) exceed two. Similar to the females results, all the 14 variables showed high level of variation ($V>22\%$).

Fig. 2. Histogram of eigenvalues males (M) and females (F) in corresponding factors.

Because similar values of variables Var13 and Var14 (grey collar of sells), correlation between factors and variables appear the same too; ($r=-0.855$). Another

pair of variables are Var10 and Var11 ($r=-0.801$). Var12 correlates with Factor 2, as well as Var1 correlates with Factor 3 (Table 4).

Table 4.

Factor analysis results (males, $n_M=55^*$)

Variables	Factors			
	1	2	3	4
Var1	0.361	0.405	0.798	-0.018
Var2	0.443	0.430	0.496	0.192
Var3	0.206	0.335	0.712	-0.156
Var4	0.376	0.669	-0.613	-0.075
Var5	0.457	0.319	-0.322	-0.098
Var6	0.087	0.613	-0.646	-0.082
Var7	0.506	-0.679	0.007	-0.518
Var8	0.064	0.054	0.392	-0.514
Var9	0.453	-0.714	-0.183	-0.313
Var10	0.855	0.145	-0.076	-0.479
Var11	0.855	0.145	-0.076	-0.479
Var12	-0.784	0.208	0.024	-0.536
Var13	-0.801	0.173	0.011	-0.542
Var14	-0.801	0.173	0.011	-0.542
Expl.Var	4.56	2.51	2.48	2.05
Prp.Totl %	32.5	17.6	16.9	14.6

*Note: n_M – males' number

Discussion

Models of the physical activity according self-evaluation of medical students developed in this research have been completed recent studies regarding self-evaluations and appearance by female medicine, evaluation of a body height and weight harmony among university students [1,2]. Although, the research was dedicated to the physical activity of medical students, students of other specialties [19]. Correlations between physical activity and body dissatisfaction, lifestyle, and nutritional status among university students are studied too. [20].

The results of this study correlate with well-known scientific publications regarding the Relationship Between Sedentary Lifestyle, Physical Activity and Stress in University Students and Their Life Habits (A Scoping Review with PRISMA) [21]. Furthermore, physical fitness evaluation level correlate with enhancing mental health, well-being and active lifestyles of university students by means of physical activity and exercise research programs [22]. Physical activity levels and sedentary behaviour according to sex, age, BMI, academic year, and country among medical students were confirm during studies in different universities not only of medical profile, but many other too [23,24]. Leisure-time physical activity, occupational physical activity and the physical activity paradox in healthcare workers.

Conclusions

Modeling of the physical activity according self-evaluation of medical students showed their professional preparation. Participation in this research should be considerate as an effective way of education. All the fourteen studied variables showed a high level of variation ($V > 22\%$). The purpose of the research was reached using development of models of the physical activity according self-evaluation of the medical students. This goal was achieved by solving the problems of providing a self-evaluation questionnaire of medical students.

Highlights

Factor analysis has been adopted for study of the results of physical activity questionnaire. Four factors were extracted during evaluation of males' students (with eigenvalues 4.56, 2.51, 2.48, 2.05) and five factors – females' students (with eigenvalues 4.74, 3.08, 2.05, 1.76, 1.07) correlation between variances was determined as strong ($r=0.7$, $p=0.05$).

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